

The Effectiveness of Employing Blended Learning on Sixth-grade Students' Achievements and Reflective Thinking Skills Development in Islamic Education in the United Arab Emirates

Osama Mohammad Ali Diabat, Majed Zaki Aljallad

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 14, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: December 19, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Blended Learning, Achievement, Reflective Thinking, The Subject Of Islamic Education</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4374738</p>	<p><i>This study aims to find out the effect of blended learning on the Achievement and development of reflective thinking of sixth-grade students in the subject of Islamic education in the United Arab Emirates. The study sample consists of two groups of sixth-grade students from Al-Andalus Private Academy school in AlAyn city. The students were divided in to two groups: an experimental group of (25) students who were taught by using the blended learning method, and a control group of (23) students who were taught by the conventional methods. To achieve the objectives of the study, a semi-experimental research method was employed as well as two tools: the achievement test and the reflective thinking scale, whose validity and reliability were ensured. The results showed statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the two groups in the post-achievement test favoring the experimental group. Also, the results showed that there were statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the two groups in the reflective thinking scale favoring the experimental group. Finally, the study recommended the importance of using blended learning method in teaching Islamic education.</i></p>

1. Introduction

The present era is witnessing a massive techno-scientific revolution and technological development, leading to the emergence of many developments and successive changes in the field of technology that have contributed to the development of methods and styles of teaching, and whose impact is felt in the fields of science and knowledge. Nevertheless, the methods of teaching Islamic education need constant development, hence the growing need for finding new methods and methods in order to keep up with these challenges in a modern way; to use unconventional patterns and methods that are distant from stagnation and indoctrination; to develop the ability to think and conduct research; and to make the learner an active learner and a lover of science and knowledge.

In light of the technological development and progress in the field of education and the future vision of the United Arab Emirates 2021, which aims to develop and enhance the educational system in an interactive environment, the Emirati Ministry of Education has been keen to develop its curricula in accordance with quality educational standards and outcomes and to provide schools with modern technologies and educational means. This allows the teacher to integrate these sources and adapt them in various forms in order to increase learning opportunities for learners and to develop their ability to think and research in the acquisition and development of knowledge (Ministry of Education, 2014).

Blended learning is considered one of the most widespread forms of educational technology in the late nineties. In fact, it is a form of e-learning that developed into interconnected programs, and some researchers view it as a substitute for e-learning (Al-Hashimi, Soman, Al-Khatib, Fakhry, and Al-Muwajdah, 386: 2010). In the same context, Graham (2004) views blended learning as learning that combines computer learning systems with face-to-face education, and Milheim (2006) views it as learning that combines the characteristics of both classroom and online education in an integrated model that benefits from the best available technologies for each.

Blended learning is instrumental in achieving interaction and motivation towards learning the subject of Islamic education through increasing the learners' attachment to the available learning programs, and developing their abilities and skills. Makhdoom et al. (2013) believe that the combination of traditional face-to-face education and e-learning through the Internet creates an interactive and complementary environment for both the teacher and his/her students. Due to the fact that blending learning allows for the possibility of learning all day long outside the classroom, learners can watch lessons repeatedly within different time frames (Eryilmaz, 2015). This provides learners with a great degree of flexibility to choose when and where to learn, and provides each of them with opportunities to learn according to their own ability and speed (Voci & Young, 2001). Hence blended learning is considered one of the best kinds of education that employ modern technology since we cannot dispense with or ignore the current educational system which blended learning attempts to develop and

improve according to the technological developments that we are experiencing today (Medina, 2018; Spring & Graham, 2017).

In addition, Reflective thinking is considered one of the types of thinking that require higher mental capacities. Indeed, it is crucial in developing students' ability and helping them to solve problems logically and not randomly; in directing thinking to specific goals since this requires analyzing the various elements of a given situation; and in searching for internal relationships (Afifi, 2018).

Considering the subject of Islamic education in the United Arab Emirates - and its importance for a comprehensive and integrated development of the learner's personality-it allows the learner to practice and develop thinking because it is closely interrelated with reflective thinking. This is evident in Quranic verses, Hadith, and various activities and examples that encourage consideration and contemplation of the vocabulary of the great universe. Due to the importance of reflective thinking, several studies have focused on studying it and searching for appropriate strategies and methods for its development. Indeed, the results of studies such as those of (Arar, 2019), (Alfara, 2021), (Yim, Ching & Long, 2017), (Hsieh and Chen, 2012), (Alabdullat and Wishah, 2019) and (Lim & Angelique, 2011) indicate a positive effect on improving achievement and developing the capacity for reflective thinking, and they assert the importance of teaching and acquiring its skills in a variety of teaching methods.

In addition, numerous studies in different disciplines assert the importance of employing blended learning in the educational process. The results of studies such as those of (Utami, 2018), (al-Massad, 2017), (Basiran, 2017), (Al-Saqaria, 2018), (Kintu & Zhu, 2016) and (Abdulrahman, Siddiq, and Ahmad, 2019) indicate its effectiveness in achievement and developing multiple skills and useful aspects, as well as enhancing the teacher's role through the use of environments supported by technological developments in curricula. Indeed, technology has become an integral part of the learning process and an imperative that is bound up with the smallest details of our lives, affecting students' achievement and the development of their reflective thinking. What distinguishes this study from its predecessors is its aim, which is to reveal the effect of using blended learning on achievement and developing reflective thinking among sixth-grade students in the subject of Islamic education in a sample of sixth-grade students in the United Arab Emirates.

Problem of the Study:

Modern information and communication technology have contributed to the development and change of education into an interactive system between students and teachers, and to the emergence of innovative educational methods based on technical tools and various effective media.

The attractive educational environment that incorporates educational technologies and programs well suited to the curriculum plays a big role in building skills, enhancing experiences, deepening understanding, and achieving sustainability in lifelong education (Ministry of Education, 2017).

Through the experience of the researchers in education, they recognized the need to employ methods based on educational technology in teaching Islamic education, especially in light of the current circumstances of the Coronavirus (COVID-19), which required the dependence on blended learning and distance learning.

Moreover, several reasons stimulated the researchers to conduct a study on the effect of using blended learning on achievement and developing reflective thinking among sixth-grade students in the subject of Islamic education in the United Arab Emirates in the city of Al Ain. These reasons are: the desire of the researchers to keep up with contemporary progress and trends in education; the emphasis placed by experts and specialists in education on the importance of teaching reflective thinking and employing modern technology and strategies for its development; the positive effect they have on overcoming the problems and methods of traditional education; and the scarcity of previous studies that dealt with this subject.

Hypotheses of the Study:

The study attempted to test the following two hypotheses:

- 1- There are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the achievement of sixth-grade students in the subject of Islamic education in the United Arab Emirates due to the teaching method (blended learning, the usual method).
- 2- There are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the development of reflective thinking among sixth-grade students in the subject of Islamic education in the United Arab Emirates due to the teaching method (blended learning, the usual method)

Objectives of the Study:

The study sought to discover the effect of using blended learning on achievement and developing reflective thinking among sixth-grade students in the subject of Islamic education.

The Importance of the Study:

The importance of the study lies in two aspects:

First: the theoretical importance:

The importance of the study lies in the fact that it represents an addition to the enrichment of the educational literature and library concerning the effect of using blended learning on achievement and the development of reflective thinking, considering the scarcity, as far as the researchers know, of studies that dealt with this

subject. The study is also a starting point for conducting similar studies in different educational stages and with other variables.

Second: the practical importance:

The study may benefit those in charge of preparing and developing Islamic education curricula by designing educational activities and situations that make use of blended learning techniques and strategies. This study can also help to provide Islamic education teachers with new ideas that contribute to the development of achievement and reflective thinking, as well as benefiting from its tools, results, and variables in conducting similar future studies.

Terms of the Study and Procedural Definitions:

The most important terms of the study and its procedural definitions are as follows:

Blended learning: blended learning is defined as: a combination of online learning and face-to-face teaching in curriculum teaching (Cheung & Hew, 2011). Procedurally, it is defined as: a set of lessons for the second unit in the subject of Islamic education, which was designed and taught through an integrated combination of traditional learning that takes place in the classroom, and electronic learning through the computer and the Internet to help sixth grade learners to improve their achievement and reflective thinking.

Academic achievement: procedurally, it is defined as the amount of knowledge and information that a student acquires through his/her study of the topics of the second unit in the Islamic education book for the sixth grade. It is measured by the grade that the students obtain in the achievement test that is designed for the purposes of this study.

Reflective thinking: procedurally, it is defined as the ability of sixth-grade students to interact with educational situations through the mental processes that they practice in order to reach a solution to the problems they face and make realistic and logical decisions. It is measured by the grade that students obtain in the reflective thinking scale of the subject of Islamic education, which was designed for the purposes of this study.

Limits of the Study:

The study has the following limits:

- Spatial limits: the study was applied to a sample of sixth grade students at Al-Andalus Private Academy School in Al Ain City, the United Arab Emirates.
- Temporal limits: the first semester of the academic year: 2019-2020.
- Objective limits: the two tools of the study, represented by the achievement test and the reflective thinking scale.
- Human limits: sixth-grade students, who are 48 studying Islamic education during the first semester of 2019-2020, and divided into two groups: experimental and control.

Research Methodology:

The semi-experimental method was used in this study, by using two equivalent groups, the experimental group and the control group, because it is most suitable for the nature of the study and the achievement of its objectives. The following figure shows the design of the study:

EG: O1 O2X O1 O2

CG: O1 O2 O1 O2

EG refers to the experimental group, CG to the control group, (O1) to the achievement test, (O2) to the reflective thinking scale, and (X) to the experimental treatment.

The Study population and its Members:

The study population included sixth-grade students enrolled in government and private schools affiliated with the Al Ain Educational Office in the United Arab Emirates in the first semester of the academic year (2019-2020), amounting to about (9.003) students according to the statistics of the Ministry of Education in 2019 for students registered in the city of Al Ain.

The study members consisted of (48) sixth-grade students at the Al-Andalus Private Academy School, affiliated with the Ministry of Education (Al Ain Education Office) in Al Ain in the United Arab Emirates. The study members were deliberately chosen, due to the availability of conditions that help to conduct the study. Two groups were chosen from the sixth-grade students in the school and were divided randomly into an experimental group of (25) students who were taught using blended learning, and a control group of (23) students who studied in the usual manner.

The Two Tools of the study:

To achieve the objectives of the study, two tools were used, as follows:

First: the achievement test

The achievement test was prepared consisting of (25) multiple-choice paragraphs with four alternatives, with each paragraph having one correct answer. When formulating the test paragraphs, the researchers took into account the whole of the behavioral objectives to be measured, being represented by the content of the study unit and the specifications table, as well as linguistic clarity and correctness, and a class duration of (45) minutes.

Validity of the achievement test

To verify the validity of the achievement test, it was presented to a group of arbitrators to show the significance of validity; to check the linguistic formulation and correctness of expressions, and the suitability of the questions to the levels of the teaching objectives; and to amend, delete or add any standards or indicators they deem appropriate.

Reliability of the achievement test

To ensure the reliability of the test, the reliability coefficient was calculated using the internal consistency method according to Coder Richardson's equation 20-, amounting to (0.86). These values are appropriate for the purposes of this study.

Second: The reflective thinking scale

After reviewing and being guided by the theoretical literature of reflective thinking and relevant research and studies, a reflective thinking scale consisting of (20) paragraphs was prepared according to the five skills of reflective thinking (visual skill, skill in detecting fallacies, skill in reaching conclusions, skill in giving convincing explanations, and skill indeveloping suggested solutions). Each skill included four paragraphs that measure the extent to which sixth-grade students possess the skills of reflective thinking.

Validity of the reflective thinking scale

To verify the validity of the reflective thinking scale, it was presented to a group of arbitrators to show the significance of the validity of the paragraphs to be measured and their suitability for the levels of sixth-grade students; to check the linguistic formulation and correctness of expressions; and to amend, delete or add any standards or indicators they deem appropriate.

Reliability of the reflective thinking scale

To ensure the reliability of the scale, the reliability coefficient was calculated using the internal consistency method according to the Coder Richardson equation 20-, amounting to (0.87). These values are appropriate for the purposes of this study.

Procedures for conducting the study experiment

After reviewing the theoretical literature and the studies relevant to the subject of the study, the two study tools were prepared and the significance of their validity and reliability was ensured. Then the study population was identified from the sixth grade students, and Al-Andalus Academy School in Al Ain was chosen to be the location of the study, where two groups were randomly chosen from the sixth grade, one representing the experimental group and the other the control group. The two researchers also obtained two communications from Al Ain University and the Department of Education and Knowledge to facilitate their mission. Then the study tools were applied to the members of the sample. Finally, the data were entered and statistically analyzed using the (SPSS) program, and the results were obtained and discussed.

Results of the Study and Discussion

First: the results related to the first hypothesis, which states that: "There are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the achievement of sixth-grade students in the subject of Islamic education in the United Arab Emirates due to the teaching method (blended learning, the usual method)."

To verify the validity of this hypothesis, the arithmetic means and the standard deviations of the performance of the study members in the pre- and post-achievement test of the sixth-grade students in the subject of Islamic education were calculated according to the different teaching methods and the group variable (experimental, control), as shown in Table (1):

Table (1): The arithmetic means and standard deviations of sixth-grade students' grades in the subject of Islamic education in the achievement test for the pre- and post-measurement according to the group (experimental, control)

		Pre-Assessment		Post-Assessment	
Group	Count	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation
Experimental	25	11	4.193	18.40	4.481
Control	23	10.22	3.692	12.00	4.824
Total	48	10.63	3.939	15.33	5.620

As it is clear in Table (1), there are apparent differences between the arithmetic means of the grades of sixth-grade students in the subject of Islamic education in the achievement test in the pre- and post-measurements according to the group (experimental, control). To find out whether these apparent differences are statistically

significant, the one-way analysis of variance (one-way ANCOVA) was used for the post-measurement of the achievement test as a whole according to the group (experimental, control) after neutralizing the effect of the pre-measurement they have. The following shows these results in Table (2).

Table (2): The results of the one-way ANCOVA of the post-measurement of the grades of sixth-grade students in the subject Islamic education in the achievement test according to the group (experimental, control) after neutralizing the effect of the pre-measurement they have.

Source of variance	sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean sum of squares	F value	Level of Significance	ETA Square η^2
Pre-measurement	397.965	1	397.965	30.046	.000	.400
Group	401.534	1	401.534	30.315	.000	.403
Error	596.035	45	13.245			
Total	1484.667	47				

Table (2) shows that there are statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the grades of sixth-grade students in the subject of Islamic education in the achievement test according to the group (experimental, control). F value is (30.315) with a statistical significance of (0.000), which is a statistically significant value, which means that there is an effect for the group. As it is evident from Table (2), the teaching method had a major effect, as the value of ETA square (η^2) interpreted (40.3%) of the interpreted (predicted) variance in the dependent variable, which is the achievement test.

This may be attributed to the blended learning environment, which is characterized by the ability to choose the best means for each educational goal; to the increase in interaction between students, educational content and learning resources on the one hand and between students and the teacher on the other hand; and to peer reactions while carrying out classroom and home activities. All of these aspects create a stimulating and enriching learning environment for students and reflect positively on the level of their achievement.

In order to identify which group is favored by the differences, the modified arithmetic means and standard errors were extracted according to the group, as shown in Table (3).

Table (3): The modified arithmetic means and standard errors for the achievement test according to the group (experimental, control)

Group	Modified post arithmetic mean	Standard error
Experimental	18.122	.730
Control	12.303	.761

The results in Table (3) indicate that the differences are in favor of the experimental group that was exposed to the blended learning in comparison to the control group members. This result indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis and its statement: "There are statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the average grades of the students of the control and experimental groups in the post-achievement test."

This can be attributed to the various characteristics of this kind of learning, which provides many opportunities for learning in a variety of ways and in interesting and enjoyable ways, which in turn facilitate the delivery, understanding and assimilation of information. Hence this kind of learning differs from the traditional teaching methods that students are accustomed to, especially in the subject of Islamic education, which contributed to increasing the learners' desire to learn and look for information that supports their learning and enriches their experience; to deepening understanding and comprehension of new ideas; and to retaining information for a longer period.

This result agrees with the results of the studies of (Utami, 2018), (al-Massad, 2017), (Saqaria, 2018) and (Kintu & Zhu, 2016), which indicate the effectiveness of blended learning in achievement and the development of positive attitudes.

Second: The results related to the second hypothesis, which states: "There are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the development of reflective thinking among sixth-grade students in the subject of Islamic education in the United Arab Emirates due to the teaching method (blended learning, the usual method)."

To verify the validity of this hypothesis, the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the sixth-grade students' grades in the subject of Islamic education were calculated on the reflective thinking scale in the pre- and post-measurements according to the group (experimental, control), as shown in Table (4):

Table (4): The arithmetic means and standard deviations of sixth-grade students' grades in the subject of Islamic education on the reflective thinking scale for the pre- and post-measurements according to the group (experimental, control)

Group	Number	Pre-Measurement		Post-Measurement	
		Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation
Experimental	25	10.40	2.828	15.16	1.841
Control	23	9.00	2.576	9.78	1.930
Total	48	9.73	2.773	12.58	3.293

It is evident from Table (4) that there are apparent differences between the arithmetic means of the sixth-grade students' grades in the subject of Islamic education on the reflective thinking scale in the pre- and post-measurements according to the group (experimental, control). To find out whether these apparent differences are statistically significant, the one-way analysis of variance (one-way ANCOVA) was used for the post-measurement of the reflective thinking scale as a whole according to the group (experimental, control) after neutralizing the effect of the pre-measurement they have. The following shows these results in Table(5):

Table (5): The results of the one-way ANCOVA of the post-measurement of the grades of sixth-grade students in the subject of Islamic education on the reflective thinking scale according to the group (experimental, control) after neutralizing the effect of the pre-measurement they have.

Source of variance	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean sum of squares	F value	Level of significance	ETA square η^2
Pre-measurement	43.603	1	43.603	16.396	.000	.267
Group	266.152	1	266.152	100.082	.000	.690
Error	119.670	45	2.659			
Total	509.667	47				

Table (5) shows that there are statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the sixth-grader students' grades in the subject of Islamic education on the reflective thinking scale according to the group (experimental, control). F value is (16.396) with a statistical significance of (0.000), which is a statistically significant value, which means that there is an effect of the group.

Table (5) shows also that the teaching method had a major effect, as the value of ETA square (η^2) interpreted (69%) of the interpreted (predicted) variance in the dependent variable, which is the scale of the reflective thinking.

In order to identify which group is favored by the differences, the modified arithmetic means and standard errors were extracted according to the group, as shown in Table (6).

Table (6):The modified arithmetic means and standard errors for the reflective thinking scale according to the group (experimental, control)

Group	Modified post arithmetic mean	Standard error
Experimental	14.919	.332
Control	10.045	.346

The results in Table (6) indicate that the differences are in favor of the experimental group that was exposed to the blended learning in comparison to the control group members.

This can be explained in the light of using blended learning in teaching, which helped to enrich knowledge and raise the quality and efficiency of the educational process, as it includes a wide range of different activities and applications that are conducted throughout the lesson stages, which raise the level of motivation to learn; engage students in an integrated and interactive educational process; and activate their previous knowledge and render it a starting point to determine what will be learned. All of these aspects contributed to attracting students' attention, stimulating pleasure and suspense, and enhancing their reflective thinking.

This result agrees with the results of the studies of(Hsieh and Chen, 2012), (Yim, Ching & Long, 2017), (Arar, 2019), (Lim & Angelique, 2012), and (Abu Shreikh, 2017) that indicate the effectiveness of employing modern programs and strategies in developing reflective thinking and its importance in the educational process.

Recommendations

- The importance of integrating blended learning into the lessons and activities of Islamic education and other academic subjects, along with including teaching models based on blended learning in the teacher's guide.
- The need to integratereflective thinking skills in multiple real educational situations when planning and developing the curriculum.
- The need to spread technical awareness among students and train them to use modern technologies in teaching Islamic education and other school subjects.
- Training Islamic education teachers in different grades to employ blended learning with its various methods and strategies in teaching.

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Author Information

Osama Mohammad Ali Diabat
Al Ain University/Al Ain, UAE.

Prof. Majed Zaki Aljallad
Al Ain University/Al Ain, UAE.
